

Synthesis of Muramyl Dipeptide Derivatives of a Decapeptide Gonadotropine Releasing Hormone

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A synthetic immunomodulator glycopeptide *N*-acetyl muramyl-L-alanyl-D-isoglutamine is conjugated to a synthetic hormone, luteinising hormone releasing hormone (LHRH) through a lysine bridge at α - or ϵ -amino position of lysine. The synthesis of the compounds are discussed.

GONADOTROPIN release hormone (GnRH or LHRH) is an important biological molecule regulating fertility in both males and females. The structure of this hormone, the decapeptide was elucidated by Schally¹ and Guillemin². Its chemical synthesis is well established. Several analogs have been made having agonistic and antagonistic actions^{3,4}.

The immunisation against this hormone can block fertility as demonstrated by both active and passive immunisation studies⁵⁻⁹. In order to render this molecule immunogenic, the decapeptide was conjugated to a carrier protein such as tetanus toxoid (TT). More recently a totally synthetic glycopeptide was reported with immunogenic properties¹⁰. Such vaccines, totally synthetic, do not entail hyperimmunisation against the carrier and are thus useful. The linkage of the adjuvant *N*-acetyl muramyl-L-alanyl-D-isoglutamine (muramyl

trifluoromethane sulphonic acid (TFMS) (Aldrich) were used. Dimethyl formamide (DMF) was purified¹¹, and dichloromethane was distilled over P₂O₅ and stored in brown bottles. Ether was dry and peroxide-free. All other reagents were of analytical grade. Sephadex G-10 (Pharmacia) was used.

Amino acid analysis was made by hydrolysing the sample with constant boiling 6*N* HCl in evacuated sealed tube at 110° for 22 h and analysed on a LKB 4101 amino acid analyser.

Final purification of the conjugates were performed by reversed phase high performance liquid chromatography in a LKB HPLC instrument using RP-C₁₈ column.

dipeptide or MDP) to the hormone is possible through a lysine bridge at α - or ϵ -amino position of lysine. This communication describes the procedure by which attachment can be realised at the desired position.

Experimental

LHRH free acid was provided by N.I.H. (Courtesy Dr. C. Bialy), and MDP and MDP-Lys were from C.D.R.I., Lucknow, α -*t*-butyloxycarbonyl- ϵ -benzyloxycarbonyl-L-lysine [BOC(*Z*)-Lys] (Bachem), *N*-ethyl-*N*-(3-dimethylamino)propylcarbodiimide (EDC) and 1-hydroxybenzotriazole (HOBT) (Sigma) and trifluoroacetic acid (TFA) and

trifluoromethane sulphonic acid (TFMS) (Aldrich) were used. Dimethyl formamide (DMF) was purified¹¹, and dichloromethane was distilled over P₂O₅ and stored in brown bottles. Ether was dry and peroxide-free. All other reagents were of analytical grade. Sephadex G-10 (Pharmacia) was used.

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MDP

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Synthesis of LHRH—Lys—OH (A): The synthesis of (A) is shown in Scheme 1.

Scheme 1

Z-Lys-OH (1): Boc(Z)-Lys (500 μ mol, 190 mg) was reacted with 50% TFA-CH₂Cl₂ (20 ml) for 30 min with occasional stirring. It was then evaporated to dryness under reduced pressure. The residue was washed with CH₂Cl₂ and again evaporated to dryness, and the operation was repeated thrice. The residue was then treated with distilled water and the resulting white precipitate was filtered and dried under reduced pressure, (128 mg); homogeneous on tlc in 1-butanol (30) - acetic acid (6) - H₂O (16) - pyridine (30); ninhydrin test positive.

LHRH-Lys(Z)-OH (2): LHRH free acid (50 μ mol, 59 mg) was reacted with 1-hydroxybenzotriazole (27 mg, 200 μ mol) and *N*-ethyl-*N'*-(3-dimethylamino)propylcarbodiimide (19 mg, 100 μ mol) in DMF (3 ml) for 7 h at room temperature with stirring. Then **1** (28 mg, 100 μ mol) was added to it and the reaction was continued for 48 h. The compound was eluted in the void volume when separated on Sephadex G-10 in 10% acetic acid - water, (68 mg); homogeneous on tlc in 1-butanol (30) - acetic acid (7) - water (16) - pyridine (20); ninhydrin test negative; Ehrlich test positive; Pauley test positive.

LHRH-Lys-OH (3): Compound **2** (57.6 mg, 40 μ mol, was reacted with TFMS (0.141 ml, 1.6 mmol), anisole (70 μ l) and 1,2-ethanedithiol (2 μ l) for 2 h at room temperature with occasional stirring. The compound was then precipitated by the addition of cold dry ether. It was filtered and the residue washed well with ether and dried under reduced pressure. The compound was eluted in the void volume when separated on Sephadex G-10 in 5% acetic acid - water, (42 mg); homogeneous on tlc in 1-butanol (30) - acetic acid (6) - water (16) - pyridine (20); ninhydrin test positive.

MDP

LHRH-Lys-OH (A): For a typical conjugation MDP (7.4 mg, 15 μ mol) was added to 1-hydroxybenzotriazole (8.2 mg, 60 μ mol) and *N*-ethyl-*N'*-(3-dimethylamino)propylcarbodiimide (5.7 mg, 30 μ mol) in 10% DMF-H₂O (1 ml). After 8 h stirring at room temperature, **3** (39.2 mg, 30 μ mol) in 80% DMF-H₂O (0.5 ml) was added and the reaction was allowed to continue for 48 h. The conjugate eluted in the void volume when separated on Sephadex G-10 in 5% Ac-OH-H₂O (Fig. 1). Fraction (aa) were pooled, lyophilised and finally purified on semi-preparative hplc RP-C₁₈ column (Fig. 2). The homogeneity of the compound was confirmed by analytical hplc as shown in Fig. 3; yield 19.4 mg. Amino acid analysis confirmed the composition of the conjugate (Table 1).

LHRH

Synthesis of MDP-Lys-OH (B): The synthesis of (B) was carried out according to the reported method¹⁰ (Scheme 2).

Fig. 1. Purification of the conjugates A and B on Sephadex G-10 column (1.7 x 95 cm), flow rate = 45 ml h⁻¹, fractions collected = 5 ml each: (—) conjugate (A) and (---) conjugate B, (aa) and (b) pooled fractions.

Fig. 2. Purification of the conjugates (A) and (B) on semi-preparative RP-C₁₈ hplc column, flow rate 1 ml min⁻¹; eluting gradient 0.1% TFA-H₂O and 0.1% TFA-CH₃CN: (—) conjugate (A) and (---) conjugate (B); pooled fractions shown by the cuts.

TABLE 1—AMINO ACID ANALYSIS OF (A) AND (B)

Amino acids	Observed ratio ^a	
	(A)	(B)
Ser	1.0 (1.0)	0.96 (1.0)
Glu	2.3 (2.0)	2.04 (2.0)
Pro	1.1 (1.0)	0.88 (1.0)
Gly	1.88 (2.0)	2.00 (2.0)
Ala	1.94 (1.0)	0.98 (1.0)
Leu	1.80 (1.0)	0.96 (1.0)
Tyr	1.39 (1.0)	0.89 (1.0)
His	1.84 (1.0)	0.92 (1.0)
Lys	1.12 (1.0)	1.20 (1.0)
Arg	1.22 (1.0)	0.91 (1.0)

^aExpected amino acid ratio are in the parenthesis.

